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Online ELT Practicum: Views of Student Teachers, Cooperating Teachers and Faculty Supervisors

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Abstract

Teaching practicum is a vital and challenging phase of English Language Teaching (ELT) teacher education in which student teachers experience their first teaching practices. In line with the global pandemic status quo, official regulations that led educational activities at state primary schools and universities to be carried out online, have also changed the modes and means in the practices and experiences of in-service and pre-service ELT teachers. Therefore, in respect of three participant groups of the practicum process as student teachers, cooperating teachers and university supervisors, it is essential to examine the impact of this new coercive teaching practice system on them. This study attempts to gain insight into the teaching practicum period that ELT student teachers, cooperative teachers and university supervisors cooperatively carried out fully online through English lessons administered by state primary schools. The results elicited by the participants' views on online practicum revealed that pupil-related issues like their low attendance and participation in online English lessons and technological problems such as internet access or computer-related malfunctions were compelling factors for student teachers and cooperative teachers. Regarding practicum performances, cooperative teachers confirmed student teachers' technological skills and the use of a variety of web 2.0 tools in their practices was found as an opportunity for student teachers to develop their teaching skills.

Keywords: ELT Teaching Practicum, Online Teaching Practicum, Online EFL Teaching, Teacher Training

1. Introduction

The global pandemic named Covid-19 started at the end of 2019 and caused a drastic change in the course of events throughout the world. Afterwards, countries all over the world took precautions to prevent the spread of pandemics and went restrictions on almost all dimensions of societies to limit human interaction. Hence, many fields are intensively influenced by the restrictions like health sector, economy, transportation, traveling, trade and indeed education. In 196 countries like Germany, Italy, France, China and Turkey started to provide fully distance education from the second half of (Spring term) 2019-2020 academic year. After March 2020 in Turkey, K-12 lessons began to be given through a TV channel (EBATV) directed by the Ministry of National Education (MoNE) and then schools were registered to lunched into online lessons where teachers could carry out via internet platforms (i.e. zoom) besides limited face to face lessons in the beginning next term (Fall 2020-2021). According

to Turkish MoNE national formal education statistics, more than 18 million students at K12 level (8.8% at private schools) received education by the 2019-2020 academic year (MoNE, 2020). Higher education in Turkey where 7.5 students study at 207 universities, also swiftly passed on online education by March 2020 (CoHE, 2020), universities established and/or advanced their distance learning platforms and started to carry out all lessons online still continued till the end of the 2020-2021 Spring term. In terms of teaching practicum, which is an obligatory course to graduate from all teacher education programs in Turkey, MoNE's Teacher Training and Development General Directorate decided to carry out the practicum process online by October 2020 and necessary regulations and contributions between the MoNE and Faculties of Education were established to make the decision operative. The process came into effect by Spring term of 2021 officially and the online practicum lasted 12 weeks by the participation of cooperation of teacher candidates, cooperating teachers and university supervisors. That is, teaching practicum has been carried out online for the first time in its history in the country. Teaching practicum itself has always been a focus of interest in teacher training/education field, in English Language Teaching (ELT) either, as it is a critical component of teacher education which serves the necessary transition of students teachers from theory and knowledge into real life teaching practices.

Including initial teaching practices, teaching practicum program has a critical role in teacher training where student teachers undergo a considerable transformation enables them to form a teacher identity and think about teaching to cope better with classroom realities they may encounter in the future. During the practicum, student teachers can enhance their teaching knowledge and skills and form a cognitive mindset of a language teacher should have by carrying out tasks, practicing under the supervision of mentoring teachers (Fang, 1996; Grudnoff, 2011; YUSn & Lee, 2014). On practicum, Farrel (2008) underlines that "One of the biggest influences of the teacher education course in terms of perceived excitement and development among learner teachers is the field based experiences they encounter because they are conducted in real classrooms." Arslan & İlin (2018) point out that practicum has a significant effect on teacher candidates that create awareness teaching-related issues in real contexts. During the practicum, student teachers may question themselves as teachers, they are more engaged with understanding their own classroom, learning from their mentor teacher, and, eventually, mastering the art of language teaching (Brinton & Holten, 1989).

In ELT teacher education, teaching practice is the ultimate key component of the process through which student teachers' content and pedagogic knowledge and teaching skills are actualized and tested, early language teacher identities are to be formed and initial steps are taken towards a lifetime teaching career. The practicum process is already quite challenging as a part of teacher training programs, however, it becomes more compelling especially in English Language Teaching (ELT) context due to field specific difficulties like student-teachers may face like language anxiety (Tüm & Kunt, 2013; Gan, 2013) and instructional challenges (Yazan, 2016) such as using English as a medium of instruction and related issues like student levels of proficiency and preparing appropriate material choice. Besides all these matters, sudden transmission from face to face to online practicum is being another challenge for ELT teacher candidates to experience their first teaching in this way as well as cooperating teachers and university supervisors who also have to mentor and evaluate teacher candidates. Limited studied have been conducted so far since remote teaching dominates the on teaching practicum, indeed online ELT practicum in Turkey context is a topic to meet the needed research space.

This study examines the views of student teachers, cooperating teachers and university supervisors about 12 weeks of online teaching practicum held during the 2021 spring term. Major aim of the study is to discover the general frame of this first online experience by the help of the participants, the challenges they have been through and the opportunities that may help for future practices. The research questions to achieve this goal are posed as;

Research question 1. What are student teachers', cooperating teachers' and university supervisors' views on online ELT practicum?

Research question 2. What are the challenges about online ELT practicum according to teacher candidates, cooperating teachers and university supervisors?

2. Literature Review

Research on teaching practicum has been the focus of attention lately as it constitutes a prominent part of teacher training program, has long lasting effects to form and change mindset over teaching and also because its sensitive nature influenced by several factors including student teacher, teacher educator and cooperating teacher oriented issues (Çelik, 2008). Most of the related literature focus on teacher candidates' concerns, reflections, beliefs, perceptions, performances, stress factors, experiences in respect of teaching practicum (Brinton & Holten, 1989; Çelik, 2008; Farrel, 2008; Yan & He, 2010; Yuen & Lee, 2013; Busher, et.al., 2014; Merç, 2015; Mirici & Ölmez, 2017; Celen & Akcan, 2017; Tüfekçi-Can & Baştürk, 2018; Arslan & İlin, 2018). On the contrary, Payant & Murphy (2012) examined the practicum form the perspective of cooperating teachers, their responsibilities and challenges. Llorca (2005) looked at nonnative TESOL students from the perspective of practicum supervisors. Dakhiel (2017) attempts to find out EFL practicum characteristics considering supervisors' views.

In Covid-19 context, Koşar (2021) examined the distance practicum period started at the very beginning of Covid-19 closures when student teachers had to quit their face to face practicum placements periods and completed the process only at university part with written assignments provided by university supervisors. The research revealed that the practicum which EFL teacher candidates completed was not efficient and they did not feel prepared for teaching.

In respect of online practicum in ELT, Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison (2020) investigated online teaching placement by EFL teacher education during Covid19 closures in Chile context. They applied questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to student teachers and found that challenges outweighed the practicum's benefits. They concluded that some essentials of teaching could not develop by online placement and providers should regulate and enrich the design of such process.

Badawi (2021) conducted a research on e-practicum EFL student teachers, their instructional performances and e-teaching self-efficacy and found that e-practicum developed their self-efficacy but their performances were ineffective. The study recommended that e-practicums need to be improved to achieve desired goals.

3. Methodology

The research is based on a mixed method that has qualitative and quantitative parts to see general perspectives on online ELT practicum. The design of the study is attributed to a convergent parallel design, a mixed method (Subedi, 2016; Creswell, 2011) in which the researcher, gathers both quantitative and qualitative data, analyzes both datasets separately, compares the results from the analysis of both datasets, and makes interpretation as to whether the results support or contradict each other. The study's main concern is to get an insight about participants' views on online practicum carried out under challenging conditions which a qualitative manner would be the appropriate perspective, however, to understand the process deeply, it is important to find out shared views and common points agreed by most of the participants to see the main picture of the process. Therefore, open-ended questions to elicit qualitative data while semi-closed questions that enable participants' yes-no answers give a quantitative texture to support a broader sense mix methodology to achieve the goal of the study.

3.1. Participants

Three participants groups were involved in the research by who online practicum was carried out:

Teacher Candidates /Student Teachers (ST): 15 senior students (fourth grade) from English Language Teaching Department of a faculty of education at a state university in Turkey

Cooperating Teachers / School Advisors (CT) : 13 experienced English teachers who work at state schools of MoNE and who are also qualified for practicum advisory. Teachers involved the research were teaching English at primary school levels during the practicum (mainly 6.,7. And 8. grades).

University Supervisors (US): 6 Lecturers of English Language Teaching (ELT) department of a faculty of education at a state university in Turkey.

The research was restricted to a city located in the south region of Turkey where participants related to the ELT department of the university in that city. Sampling is random stratified type in which all three groups of participants share the same attribute to attain the education goal, namely a successful teaching practicum.

Participants' roles in practicum process:

Teacher candidates/student teachers play major role in practicum as they have to complete the practicum process in the last semester in order to graduate. School advisors/cooperating teachers are chosen by the MoNE from experienced English teachers who have the license to be practicum advisors given by an obligatory course. They have to work assigned a group of STs by incorporating STs into their lessons, making them practice (four times teaching practice is obligatory for STs), observing them during practicing and joining the lessons that STs practice and evaluating their performances and also coordinating with university supervisors to evaluate STs' overall performance together. They also coordinate with university advisors and conduct a schedule for student teachers to practice teaching. University supervisors carry out the teaching practicum course of university part who is responsible for each STs assigned them, to provide them a joint schedule of practicing program prepared with CTs, make weekly meetings with TCs about the progress, joint their practices one by one, give them feedback and evaluate them for their performances as the final grade. General practicum grade is given jointly by CTs and USs yet major score is provided by CTs (about 70%) as their responsibility is more as they have to constantly involve two school days and at least 6 hours in a weekly school plan while following up TCs attendance and observing their in- class attitudes and performances. After the compilation of practicum process about two and a half months, up to state schools official academic calendar, CTs and USs do the grading on a joint platform of the MoNE's practicum based grading platform and successful candidates complete their practicum and get the opportunity to graduate.

3.2. Online Practicum Process

At the beginning of 2020-2021 educational calendar's spring term, it was decided by decision makers to go a hybrid education at primary and secondary schools, half face to face/half online due to pandemic restrictions to minimize human interaction. Face to face education was done two weekdays while online lessons continued to be given by school teachers via platforms (EBA TV and zoom as it had been during fall term fully online) that coordinated by the local MoNE administrators. Thus, the MoNE and the Higher Education Council decided on practicum process of all teacher training programs of Faculties of Education in Turkey to be carried online and informed faculties of education and state schools to prepare schedules according to this regulation. During the spring term, CTs' weekly plan was hybrid as two or three days face to face and two days online. Due to the current regulations, TCs had to attend only weekly online lessons to complete their practicum lasted twelve weeks in total (started by last week of February and ended mid-May) during when also CTs and USs periodically observed and evaluated them when they performed teaching.

3.3. Questionnaire

In the study, a survey comprised of five open and semi-closed were utilized to collect data. A closed ended question provides a preset response which may force limits participants to respond in a particular way, while open-ended questions present options for responding. In the present study closed-ended questions are used as the quantitative side of the analysis where yes-no answers are gathered and then given explanation of the answer to justify it is interpreted quantitatively. According to Popping (2015, p.4) "It is possible that an answer can only be understood in combination with the answer to the accompanying closed question." Creswell (2012) identifies semi-closed-ended questions as having all the advantages of open- and closed-ended questions structured as asking a closed-ended question and then asking for additional responses in an open-ended question. For instance, Item 1 (Was online teaching practicum effective and sufficient experience for you? Could you explain your answer why yes/no?) starts as a closed question followed by an open ended question giving opportunity to justify answer of the former question to avoid bias and can be described as semi-open question combines the control of the closed and semi-closed questions with the fruitfulness of the open question. The question tries to find out and specify participants' views on online practicum to undercover its strengths and weaknesses according to main characters

who carried out/perform and so able to evaluate it. Indeed, the question partially seeks answer to research question 1 that interrogates the general views about online practicum by participants.

3.4. Data collection and Analysis

Due to Covid19 restrictions, data collection procedure was done through communication platforms rather than delivering and filling forms physically. The questionnaire which has an initial consent declaration option to gather participants' views on online practicum prepared by Google forms and conveyed via WhatsApp groups with a consent declaration option. The compiled answers were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively and interpreted to achieve the main goal of the research.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Student Teachers' Views

The scope of the study centered upon three participant groups' (English teacher candidates, university and school advisors') views on online teaching practicum that was carried out last semester. First group to discuss their findings is EFL teacher candidates who underwent this period for the first time in the history of university education and the EFL teacher training field which is a fact that makes it extra significant to consider teacher candidates' (TCs) views. As a start, first item was to figure out the effectiveness and sufficiency. When effectiveness and sufficiency of the practicum were questioned, many TCs (8 out of 14) thought negative while 4 of them said yes and 2 of them said both yes and no as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Participant views on item 1

Item 1	Was online teaching practicum effective and sufficient experience for you? Could you explain your answer why yes/no			
	Participants*	Yes	No	Both (yes and no)
ST1		•		
ST2			•	
ST3		•		
ST4			•	
ST5		•		
ST6			•	
ST7			•	
ST8				•
ST9			•	
ST10			•	
ST11				•
ST12			•	
ST13		•		
ST14		•		
ST15			•	

*ST: Student Teachers

TCs who answered no to the question have reasons as follows:

ST2: We did not have a full interaction with the pupils.

ST4: We did not see the real classroom setting and I felt deficiency in classroom management.

ST6: We only had voice communication and we tried to do the teaching with the pupils we did not even see their faces.

ST7: We could not come together with pupils physically.

ST9: We do not have face-to-face teaching experience at all.

ST10: The number of pupils was limited and there was no one to one interaction.

ST12: There was no real student-teacher interaction with a sincerity and energy, we do not have the opportunity to use body language.

ST15: I do not think it was because face to face interaction with pupils would be better for the flow and the productivity.

Most of the reasons why they think the practicum was not effective and sufficient addressed to the non-existence of face to face student-teacher interaction. Participants who think the process was fully effective and sufficient simply justify their responses as follows:

ST1: I improved my skills on using web 2.0 tools, material development and classroom management. How to behave in the classroom, how to manage the control, experiencing these online was really great.

ST4: There were pupils attending the online lessons so I could prepare my lesson plans and activities, do my teaching and get feedback.

STT6: Because it was the best option under these conditions, It has been a teaching experience under extraordinary conditions.

ST7: Because when pupils attend the lesson and open up their cameras, there was a classroom environment even it was not like face to face. It was effective and sufficient as the first teaching experience.

ST14: Yes, although we were not in a face to face setting, I saw pupils quickly accustomed to online education.

Participants think the process was satisfying in terms of classroom management, preparation of material/activity and plan, pupils existence. Two participants believe the process was effective but not sufficient:

ST8: It was effective for me as it is my first teaching experience but I cannot say it was sufficient because there were many problems like very few pupils attended the lessons, and many of them did not participate activities, indeed there was zero participation in some lessons, also they frequently had connecting/internet problems.

ST11: It was effective but not sufficient; we had the chance to observe technology integrated classroom experience but I felt the deficiency of not practicing in a face-to-face classroom environment.

In Item two (in Table 2.), the preference of participants on practicum delivery type is questioned whether it should be online or face to face:

Table 2: Participants' views on item 2

Item 2	If you had a chance to choose, would you prefer online or face to face practicum?			
	Participants*	Online	Face to face	Both (partially online- face to face)
ST1		•		
ST2			•	
ST3				•
ST4			•	
ST5			•	
ST6			•	
ST7			•	
ST8		•		
ST9				•
ST10			•	
ST11			•	
ST12			•	
ST13			•	
ST14				•
ST15			•	

*ST: Student Teachers

Most of the participants (9 out of 13) who already underwent the online teaching practicum last semester, prefer to choose regular, formal face to face practicum if they had the opportunity. The face to face practicum supporters' opinions can be summed as in the following:

ST2: I'd prefer face to face so pupils would be more willing and the process would be more beneficial.

ST4: I'd prefer face to face practicum, I would have done activities, played games with children, got immediate feedback and communicated them effectively.

ST5: I prefer face to face. Although I worked at language courses, I've never had teaching experience with young learners. I believe that gaining teaching experience with learners from all age groups is very important for us because English teachers are able to teach at primary-secondary school or higher education levels.

ST6: Of course I'd prefer it face to face. Teaching would be more fruitful for both the teacher and the pupils when there is a social connection in a classroom environment. It should be with pupils to use body language and classroom management skills effectively.

ST7: I would go with face to face because I believe the place of a teachers is the classroom. And also we can only develop our teaching skills properly in the classroom.

ST10: Face to face, because we cannot interact with the pupils nor see what do in front of the camera.

ST11: If I had a chance and the conditions were normal, I would choose to attend face to face practicum.

ST12: Of course face to face because you cannot do everything in teaching online. Options are limited. It is impossible to control what students engage with, opening up white board, share the screen, these are time consuming.

ST13: I'd prefer face to face, because to teach in a real classroom with pupils would be more effective experience and also I would have had the opportunity to develop my classroom management skills.

ST15: I rather face to face cause I think online education is not appropriate for every level of pupils.

Participants believe that a face to face teaching experience would be better in terms of developing teachings skills like establishing teacher-student interaction and rapport, performing activities, student engagement and classroom management. Rest of the participants either favor of fully online or a hybrid system (half online half face to face) would be an adequate experience as in their statements:

ST1: I think It should be online so teachers can upgrade their skills in using Web2 tools, and develop online materials compatible with pupils' needs, for example they can prepare online or different activities for vocabulary teaching. Online practicum helps teachers to become experts in online teaching.

ST3: I could be half online half face to face. It is possible to create and perform more activities online.

ST8: I'd prefer it online because like every field, education renovate itself with a technology integrated understanding. I know the fact that new teachers who have one year internship training also engage with discovering the profession in their first two-three years so face to face system would be insufficient. Therefore I'd prefer online practicum.

ST9: It would be an advantage to take both, so we should be receiving both face to face and online teaching practicum experience during graduate education.

ST14: Both have pros and cons, online does not provide a full classroom setting and cause less interaction with students but it serves enormous technology use probably. We have opportunity to prepare and present a lot of Web2 tools as several that could not be used in a real classroom setting. And this helps students to develop problem solving and creative thinking skills and exposure to visual and audio content in target language.

Table 3: Participants views' on item 3

Item 3	Did you have any problems or difficulties during online practicum? (If yes, what type of...)	
Participants*	Technological problems (internet, connection, voice, camera, etc.)	Pupils' problems (attendance/ participation/ motivation/ classroom management, etc.)
ST1	•	
ST2	•	•

ST3		
ST4	•	•
ST5	•	
ST6	•	•
ST7	•	
ST8	•	
ST9	•	
ST10		•
ST11	•	•
ST12	•	•
ST13	•	
ST14		•
ST15		•

*ST: Student Teachers

Item 3 is an open ended question to find out the troubles STs had during online teaching practicum. Two main problem types yielded from the participant views; technical problems and student-oriented problems. As expected, technical problems include internet connecting problems (not connecting, fall from the net, disappear suddenly, etc.) both for research participants and pupils, troubles with computer related devices or apparatus like camera, microphone are major difficulties nearly all of STs faced during the process. Other problems can be addressed to student behaviors; no attendance, no participating to activities, unwillingness to participate activities, reluctance to answer STs' questions all of which cannot be attributed to technical (hearing/voice) problems.

Being the very first step to active teaching English in the field and one of a kind experience never that implemented before, the impression of online practicum process from the perspective of teacher candidates, with its pros and cons is worthwhile to undercover to enlighten the future teacher training conceptualizations. When they asked what has remained from this experience, positive or negative sides of the process, variety of given claims presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Participants' views on item 4

Item 4 Participants	Positive or negative, what do you remember from your online practicum experience?	
	Negative	Positive
ST1	Trying to guide students to raise hands	It was nice when students liked the video that I shared
ST2	Technical problems	Preparing and performing activities with students made a big contribution
ST3	Technical problems	When students attend to lessons and being able to do online activities as much as possible
ST4	Technical problems Nonattendance of students	Students' respect for me and for the lesson was very nice.
ST5	Few student attendances and limited interaction with them	It was a time and space saving experience
ST6	No interaction and no eye-contact with students and their attitude; they just said they did not want to participate	Having the ability to use technology better
ST7	Limited use of teaching skills that was supposed to be used in face to face education	Experiencing the easiness of teaching at home
ST8	Classroom environment lack potentials due to financial problems and inequality service	Being prepared and beneficial for the possibility of obligatory online teaching in the future
ST9	Nothing negative	Nothing positive
ST10	Difficulties in reaching education and lack of interaction that needed in language teaching	A good experience to guide how to behave under such extra-ordinary conditions (Pandemic and necessity of switching to online teaching)

ST11	Insufficient as it was not a face to face in areal classroom setting	Not in its fullest sense but provided teaching opportunity for us as unexperienced ones
ST12	Technical problems Lack of productivity in lessons Lack of interaction with students (you don't see who does what)	Silence in the classroom so it was easy to choose students
ST13	Technical problems Nonattendance of students	Feeling lucky to have at least this experience under these hard conditions and realizing that choosing to be an English teacher was the right decision.
ST14	Some of pupils' being reckless and isolate themselves from the context.	Pupils' participation their increasing curiosity when out of traditional education were really nice.
ST15	Pupils were so unwilling though we force them to participate	Nothing positive

*ST: Student Teachers

Technical problems are interaction with students at the forefront in STs reminiscence of online teaching practicum. When it comes to positive things they addresses, nearly all of them have positive feelings and thoughts especially on student centered points like their existence, respect, participation, feedback and other comments mostly meet on a common ground on that it was good for their future teaching activities in terms of its benefits, advancing the use of materials, being prepared for similar conditions, using technology better, at least having teaching experience itself. Even tough indicate many challenges mostly originated from technical issues and students, they mostly reflect upon the online practicum positively and appreciate the given opportunity.

The last open-ended question was to have idea about STs' possible suggestions for future implementations based on their online teaching practicum experience. At this point, it was aimed to point out STs offerings to light the way as compulsorily pioneers given in Table 5:

Table 5: Participants' views on item 5

Item 5	Dou have any further comments and suggestions about online teaching practicum?
Participants	Suggestions/Comments
ST1	I liked the process
ST2	I believe online education will be beneficial with a better internet substructure and by ensuring the equality for all students have access to the internet and technological devices
ST3	No suggestions/comments
ST4	Ensuring the student attendance, student number, there should be more English lessons but in an intermittent way.
ST5	It would be better to observe one class at a time broadly as there is no face to face interaction
ST6	Students might be asked to open their cameras
ST7	I think online education is appropriate and beneficial but a hundred percent online process would not be so advantageous.
ST8	Online teaching should continue after Covid19. The World is controlled through technology bases systems right now and we have to catch up with the evolution that the education field underwent. Hence, I did not have any but I observed my friends had troubles with the use of technology so there should be related courses within ELT teacher training program. curriculum.
ST9	Online teaching practicum should be given during Fall semester or at the third grade before face to face so teacher candidates can develop digital skills. Because hybrid models (online+ face to face) do exist now.
ST10	No suggestions/comments
ST11	I want conditions back to normal and face to face education carry on.
ST12	-Teacher candidates should teach topics in different skills (e.g.one teach smth. listening and the other one reading) -It is hard to follow PPP in40 minutes so pair work could be useful.

	-The number of students should be average of 10, it is hard to manage 20 or more.
	-Teacher candidates should focus more on pronunciation
ST13	No suggestions/comments
ST14	Online practicum should take part in face to face practicum.
ST15	Please, let education turn to face to face.

Most of STs make suggestions (10 out of 3) that can be addressed to improve future practices in the field. Better technological services, in-classroom applications, student centered issues (number of students, their participant to activities, their access to internet and devices; offerings intended to teacher candidates' conditions like technology course offer teacher training program, a hybrid model for practicum, skill-based practicing, pair work, etc. As pioneers, their perspectives may direct the possible next practices to overcome difficulties they had, improve the necessary parts and reinforce and the existing positive sides.

4.2. Cooperating Teachers' and University Supervisors' Views

The backbone of the study is formed a binary stakeholders play a leading role in this practicum process; STs and their advisors from university and from state school who are concurringly carry out the process through guide STs, by providing them opportunity to perform teaching, observing and evaluating their practices and finally decide their accomplishment of the practicum. In fact, since the school advisors (CTs) work closely with STs along the whole practicum period (see section 3) more than university supervisors (USs) and their responsibility and potency in evaluating STs' performance more dominant according to MoNE regulations. That is, CTs as mentors have the 70% percent of evaluation while USs' as 30% of the total score of practicum course which is formally coordinated and carried out jointly by regional MoNE and Faculties of Education. In the study, both CTs' and USs' views on online ELT teaching practicum were examined regarding two main points; one is that their experience in mentoring STs in previous face to face practicum periods, the other matter is that online practicum was their first experience that they share with STs in this respect. As a start, item 1 questioning the efficacy and sufficiency of online practicum was asked to advisors that presented in Table 6:

Table 6: Participants views' on item 1

Item 1	Was online teaching practicum effective and sufficient experience for you?	
	Yes	No
Participants*		
CT1	•	
CT2	•	
CT3	•	
CT4	•	
CT5		•
CT6		•
CT7		•
CT8		•
CT9		•
CT10		•
CT11	•	
CT12		•
CT13	•	
US1		•
US2		•
US3		•
US4		•
US5		•
US6		•

*CT: Cooperating Teacher; US: University Supervisor

In terms of Item 1, CTs' views exhibit nearly a parallel frame in which 6 of 13 participants think the online practicum was effective and sufficient while the other 7 participants favor an opposite view. On the other hand, USs' perspectives in this respect confirm that practicum was not acceptable enough. Participants who answered yes have their own reasons to justify their views as can be seen below:

CT1: It was sufficient under current conditions.

CT2: Yes it was because STs have learned 'the fundamental difficulties of teaching and find out solutions'. Being a teacher means educate and evaluate in all conditions.

CT3: I believe this new type of implementation is beneficial as it should be experienced anyway.

CT4: Yes it was sufficient.

CT11: Yes.

CT10: Under current conditions, yes it was enough.

Participants who answered negative then provided variety of explanations to justify their responds as below:

CT5: No because face to face system is more beneficial in all aspects.

CT6: No it wasn't because they didn't have the chance to see the physical classroom.

CT7: No, they (STs) should have felt the real classroom atmosphere and interacted with students.

CT8: No because student attendance was low.

CT9: It was not sufficient as it was solely online education.

CT10: No it was not because everything was theoretical, STs couldn't do practice properly and have the opportunity to interact with students.

CT12: Actually it was not enough for the sake of face to face education.

US1: Generally, it was not sufficient because problems that occurred during the online lessons effected STs negatively such as students' low attendance rate or their reluctance to participate the activities.

US2: No, because implementation would be fully effective in a face to face practicum.

US3: No, because student attendance was very low in online lessons, STs had to follow lessons with very few students.

US4: No it was not because they (STs) could not interact one on one with students, make eye contact with them also they couldn't learn classroom management.

US5: No because they did not a real teaching experience.

US6: No it was not a real teaching experience because language teaching cannot be limited to only using online materials and activities and trying to do them with very few students.

Most of CTs point of view in saying no address some issues like STs' minimum or no interaction with students, nonattendance, reluctance or demotivation of students in online lessons, and the effectiveness of face to face practicum and its felt deficiency by CTs also underlined obviously. Similar concerns are shared by USs about interaction, lack in student attendance and motivation emphasized by them. It is clear that most of advisors did not find the online practicum effective and sufficient due to common problems of online education system which makes online practicum questionable.

Participants were asked to evaluate the performances of STs as trainees by item 2 to see whether they were sufficient and whether the online practicum achieved the goal of enabling STs put theories into practice to some extent. Table 7 shows advisors' views about STs performances

Table 7: Participants' views on item 2

Item 2 Participants	Do you think the performances of teacher candidates were sufficient? Why/how so..			
	Yes	No	Both/ Partia lly Depe nds	Why/How so?
CT1	•			Because, they are within the technology.
CT2	•			They practiced teaching only online.
CT3	•			Yes, I think it was fruitful by their tendency to technology and our guidance.

CT4	•	(Just yes)
CT5	•	(Just yes)
CT6	•	(Just yes)
CT7	•	Yes they were lucky about presentations.
CT8	•	Yes they were quite equipped.
CT9	•	Yes STs were very competent and creative about using technology.
CT10	•	Yes they were very willing and enthusiastic and they really made the effort in all aspects.
CT11	•	Yes they really prepared well and their excitement could be felt even from the screen.
CT12	•	It could have been longer like two semesters
CT13	•	Yes, because they effectively used the materials and testing/evaluation sources.
US1	•	That depends on students, some of them had a good performance and they had willing to teach while others were not good as expected.
US2	•	Yes, because they did their best in handling their duties and responsibilities.
US3	•	Yes, our STs turned the conditions into a productive opportunity and prepared materials, actively attended the online lessons and presented successful performances.
US4	•	(Just no)
US5	•	Partially depends on the nature of the lesson, some STs' performances were sufficient and some of them didn't even attend the lessons.
US6	•	Some of them were successful and willing, some not.

* CT: Cooperating Teacher; US: University Supervisor

When CTs' views are examined, many of them appreciate STs' technology skills which can be a good start for the future of online teaching practicum as the teacher candidates of new generation are quite capable of using technology as an advantage in teaching practices. If it is considered that this was also CTs' first experience in teaching English online for their own students due to Covid-19 conditions that forced schools shut down, they had their own struggles in using technology and it is possible for them to notice STs capabilities and skills in this respect. Yet not surprised and impressed by STs tech skills like CTs as they may already intensively use digital tools in their academic works, but some USs confirmed STs good performances whereas others were not satisfied with some performances. Most of the participants think positive about STs practicum performances which seems online practicum did not negatively affect their willingness and skills, indeed their technological skills might have helped to advance their ability to put field specific content knowledge into practice.

The ELT practicum last (Spring) semester of 2020-2021 academic year was jointly carried out with state schools. Before the semester started, MoNE decided to go a hybrid system in primary school education (partially online and face to face). English teachers of who are CTs of the practicum process at the same time had a schedule involving both online and face to face (in-classroom) setting in their weekly lesson plan. In respect of practicum implementation, online lessons were included to practicum content, that is, STs were going to attend online lessons of their assigned CTs weekly plans. Thus, there was a face to face practicum opportunity, MoNE directed the stakeholders to carry out it fully online. When advisors were asked whether the online practicum should have done face to face shown in Table 8, most of them favored face to face option for the sake of practicum, addressing the pandemic for the carried out format back in the day, though.

Table 8: Participants' views on item 3

Item 3	Do you think the practicum should have been online or face to face last semester?			
	Participants*	Online	Face to Face	Both
CT1			•	
CT2		•		

<u>CT3</u>	•	
<u>CT4</u>	•	
<u>CT5</u>		•
<u>CT6</u>		•
<u>CT7</u>		•
<u>CT8</u>		•
<u>CT9</u>		•
<u>CT10</u>		•
<u>CT11</u>		•
<u>CT12</u>	•	
<u>CT13</u>		•
<u>US1</u>		•
<u>US2</u>		•
<u>US3</u>		•
<u>US4</u>		•
<u>US5</u>		•
<u>US6</u>		•

*CT: Cooperating Teacher; US: University Supervisor

It is understood that all advisors think that online practicum should have done face to face if it was possible providing a common sense on the values of practicum's achievements. When problems that advisors had during the online practicum, a general distribution of difficulties can be seen as presented in Table 9:

Item 4	Did you have any problems or difficulties during online practicum?			
	Participants*	No	Yes	
Technological problems (internet, connection, voice, camera, etc.)			Students oriented problems (attendance/participation/motivation/classroom management, etc.)	Other (ST oriented problems; attendance/participation/motivation/personal or instructional disagreements, institutional problems, problems with other partner advisors, etc.)
<u>CT1</u>	•			
<u>CT2</u>	•			
<u>CT3</u>		•		
<u>CT4</u>	•			
<u>CT5</u>			•	
<u>CT6</u>			•	
<u>CT7</u>			•	
<u>CT8</u>			•	
<u>CT9</u>		•		•
<u>CT10</u>				•
<u>CT11</u>		•		
<u>CT12</u>				•
<u>CT13</u>		•		
<u>US1</u>		•	•	•
<u>US2</u>				•
<u>US3</u>	•			
<u>US4</u>	•			
<u>US5</u>			•	
<u>US6</u>			•	•

*CT: Cooperating Teacher; US: University Supervisor

Among CTs and USs, 5 of them did not face any trouble and everything was fine whereas other participants provided some challenges. Among CTs experienced problems, half of them indicated student oriented problems like low attendance and participation rate and others mentioned technical problems like internet computer use failures. At this point, it is clear that CTs and STs as well as some of USs share common problems during online practicum and their responses confirmed the major aim of this in its fullest sense in trying to find out the challenges of online ELT practicum. samples from the responses are as follows:

CT9: As it was online, communication problems occurred. It was understood that teacher candidates did not have experience in handling such situations.

US1: There were connecting and technical problems. Our candidates had problems to develop and prepare proper materials. Some of candidates could not have the opportunity to do teaching practice due to very low student attendance. More significantly, since most of our candidates did not have a full command of lesson planning, practicing and evaluation, they had troubles putting recognized theoretical knowledge of face to face education into practice.

CT7: Pupils' silence caused difficulties for both sides (students and STs).

CT3: No other problems occurred except for media devices originated issues like connection break or malfunction.

As seen above, some of CTs and USs claimed that they had other type of difficulties in observing and following the lessons, STs' confusions in handling communication problems, their insufficiencies in putting theoretical knowledge into practice and lesson planning and other ST originated problems.

Lastly, as they have now enough experience to do it, advisors were asked whether they have further comments and suggestions on online practicum in ELT for the possible future practices. As advisors are like the directors of the process, their suggestions and comments are quite significant if considered by decision makers. In terms of online ELT practicum carried out under pandemic conditions for the first time, all advisors that consist of experienced English teachers working at state schools and university lecturers directly responsible for the training of English teacher candidates have right to recommend on critical topics and issues, strengths and weaknesses of the online practicum experience. In table 10, summarizes their proposals:

Table 10: Participants views on item 5

Item 5	Dou have any further comments and suggestions about online teaching practicum?
Participants	Suggestions/Comments
CT1	No suggestions/comments
CT2	The required substructure for the registration of candidates' lesson practices should be prepared for future implementations.
CT3	As online teaching become obligatory under special conditions, it is beneficial for candidates to experience it in this field too.
CT4	Teacher candidates can have the opportunity to perform more and variety of activities.
CT5	Pre-prepared materials are quite useful.
CT6	No suggestions/comments
CT7	I'd prefer it face to face.
CT8	Teacher candidates were successful and respectful. Online tools were used and students' attentions were gathered.
CT9	I hope it never happens again.
CT10	I did not have much negativities but if only I'd prefer to be face to face with students and teacher candidates and want them (STs) to see student behaviors in in-classroom setting, so we would have presented them (STs) more realistic atmosphere.
CT11	I definitely suggest face to face practicum expect for obligatory cases.
CT12	Practicum should be longer and teacher candidate should practice at all levels.

CT13	As our school were high in student participation, candidates had the opportunity to interact with students and were productive.
US1	Considering the practicum online, weekly assignments of candidates should be updated, new topics like difference and similarities between online and face to face practicum should be added to theoretic course of the practicum.
US2	Face to face is more fruitful and effective.
US3	Online practicum system did not let candidates to observe students directly and school advisors' teaching monotype and almost same lessons made it hard for them to guide teacher candidates.
US4	No suggestions/comments
US5	Out of pandemic period, some educational fields still can be go online but I think programs like medicine and teacher training should be face to face. I think online practicum is not so beneficial.
US6	Practicum might be a hybrid model covering both face to face and online lessons, it would be more fruitful for teacher candidates having traditional style experience and be active in new era' online teaching.

*CT: Cooperating Teacher; US: University Supervisor

As a shared view by some CTs and USs, the practicum should be face to face; the process was found beneficial by some of them though. The use of online materials richly by teacher candidates is underpinned whereas the necessity of some technical revisions in online teaching platforms and the need of a change in practicum's instructional content to adapt current distant education conditions are also emphasized by the participants. There are differences between STs and advisor participants that STs mostly suggest their requests solutions for the technical and student-originated issues they faced while advisors' perspectives note face to face practicum itself which can be seen in one of the comments as "*I hope it never happens again.*" (CT9) referring to compulsory online education and its difficulties.

5. Conclusion

In order to address research questions of the study seeking views of participants and challenges they indicate on online practicum, some significant points expressed by all participants listed below:

- Most of the participants have doubts about the effectiveness and sufficiency of the online practicum experience yet some views confirmed the adequacy of it under the current conditions.
- Participants' next common sense formed by the idea of the practicum they wish it was online or face to face. Not all of them but a lot of views favored face to face system, a surprisingly common choice between teacher candidates as the least experienced group and cooperating teachers as the most experienced participant group.
- When it comes to difficulties that participants had during online practicum, two types of problems come to forefront; technological problems as internet connection failures and computer related devices' malfunctions; student originated issues like low rates of attendance, their reluctance to participate activities and answer questions.
- As teaching practicum has a permanent influence on teachers' cognition, teacher identity formation and future teaching practices, students teachers were asked to indicate the reminiscence of practicum. Positive points were stressed like having opportunity to use materials and technology for teaching and at least having a chance to experience teaching for the first time officially under difficult conditions that will prepare them for future real life situations. Technological and pupils-related problems were negative sides of the process for them.
- A particular question of evaluating performances of student teachers were responded by all school cooperating teachers who found them successful and mostly appreciate their usage of materials and technology skills. Some university supervisors confirmed their achievements, others mentioned that performances depended on each teacher candidate's own case and criticized some performances specifically

on putting theories into the practice in online lessons, however they accepted the factor of challenging conditions.

- For the future attempts, the participants shared their recommendations as they experienced the very first online ELT practicum. Student teachers hope for solutions of major problems such as better technological services, pupils' attendances and motivation at online lessons. School and university advisors commented on general achievements of the practicum process and underlined the necessity of a face to face practicum for the future initiatives.

The results of the study contribute to future implementations especially when carrying out online lessons becomes a necessity for a teaching practicum process again. A better technological structure and student involvement to distance education process. Online teaching and learning, distance learning or e-learning has become necessary and prominent during Covid-19 pandemic restrictions globally that most of countries had to carry out educational activities through internet such that traditional face to face education was interrupted and remained background for a while. In such conditions, students from all levels had problems in reaching out online education due to lack of opportunities. Our study partially confirmed primary school students' difficulties in online lessons which also influenced practicum process to some extent. For instance, the fact of low student attendance rates on online lessons that also expressed by the participants of the current study might be considered by MoNE and other related decision makers to do necessary regulations and attempts to disseminate and improve distance education. Indeed, technological issues should be handled to advance the quality of online education and students' access to internet and technological devices is needed to be facilitated to provide equal training opportunities during difficult times. The study results also supported and shared some of similar recent research outcomes like the study of Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison (2020) about teacher candidates limited interaction with students and their need for a more real teaching experience and also technological issues. The general outcomes of the present research are in accordance with Badawi (2021) in respect of online practicum processes are needed to be improved to provide effective teaching practice experiences. The study results also support some facts emphasized by König (2020) et.al. that state schools should catch up with a fundamental ICT transformation. Unlike Celen & Akcan (2017) that underline ELT teacher candidates' technology skills are needed to be improved, however, student teachers' technology knowledge and skills in this research were found adequate by cooperating teachers. Although challenging sides of online practicum, student teachers' efforts to use technology as an advantage by the help of online lessons might be a great opportunity for them to achieve the goal of being 21 century teachers.

This study is limited to participants from state schools and universities and their views on ELT practicum. In further studies, the number of participants can be enhanced and the research can be deepened and amplified with a variety of quantitative and qualitative methods to reach more generalizable results.

References

- Andrew, M. & Razoumova, O. (2017). Being and becoming TESOL educators: embodied learning via practicum. *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 40(3), 174-186.
- Badawadi, M.F.A. (2021). The effect of e-practicum on developing EFL student teachers' instructional performance and e-teaching self-efficacy. *Research in Language Teaching*, 2, 16, 687-727. <https://dx.doi.org/10.21608/ssl.2021.71053.1066>
- Bao, W. (2020). COVID-19 and Online teaching in higher Education: a case study of Peking university. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies* 2 (2), 113-115.
- Brinton, D. & Holten, C. (1989). What novice teachers focus on: the practicum in TESL. *TESOL Quarterly*, 23,(2), 343-350. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3587356>.
- Busher, H., Gündüz, M., Cakmak, M., & Lawson, T. (2014). Student teachers' views of practicums (teacher training placements) in Turkish and English contexts: A comparative study. *Compare*, 45(3), 445-466.
- Çelik, M. (2008). Pre-Service EFL teachers' reported concerns and stress for practicum in Turkey. *Education and Science*, 33(150), 97-109. <http://egitimvebilim.ted.org.tr/index.php/EB/article/viewFile/634/104>.
- Celen, K.M. & Akcan, S. (2017). Evaluation of an ELT practicum programme from the perspectives of supervisors, student teachers and graduates. *Journal of Teacher Education and Educators*, 6(3), 251-274. <http://jtee.org/document/issue14/article2.pdf>.
- Creswell, J.W. (2011). *Educational research*. New Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Creswell, J.W. (2011). *Educational research: planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Boston: Pearson.

- Council of Higher Education (CoHE) (2020). Turkish higher education in days of pandemic. <https://covid19.yok.gov.tr/CTyfalar/HaberDuyuru/opinion-turkish-higher-education-in-days-of-pandemic.aspx>.
- Dakhiel, M.A. (2017). Essential characteristics of EFL practicum supervisors from their perspective. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5 (6), 1021-1029. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2017.050615.
- Farrel, T.S.C. (2008). 'Here's the book, go teach the class': ELT practicum support. *RELC*, 39(2), 226-241. DOI: 10.1177/0033688208092186.
- Flores, M. A., & M. Gago. (2020). Teacher education in times of COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal: national, institutional and pedagogical responses. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46 (4), 507-515. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1799709>.
- Gan, Z. (2013). Learning to Teach English Language in the Practicum: What Challenges do Non-Native ESL Student Teachers Face?. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2013v38n3.3>.
- Grudnoff, L. (2011). *Rethinking the practicum: limitations and possibilities*. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(3), 223-234. doi:10.1080/1359866x.2011.5883.
- Koşar, G. (2021). Distance teaching practicum: its impact on pre-service EFL teachers' preparedness for teaching. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 9 (2), 11-126. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1291724.pdf>.
- König, J.; Jäger-Biela, D.J. & Glutsch, N. (2020) Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 608-622, DOI: 10.1080/02619768.2020.1809650.
- Merç, A. (2015). Assessing the performance in EFL teaching practicum: student teachers' views. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 4(2), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v4n2p44>.
- Ministry of Education (MoNE). (2020). National education statistics formal education 2019/20. http://sgb.meb.gov.tr/meb_iys_dosyalar/2020_09/04144812_meb_istatistikleri_orgun_egitim_2019_2020.pdf.
- Mirici, İ.H. & Ölmez-Çağlar, F. (2017). Reflections on practicum experiences of non-ELT student teachers in Turkey. *ELT Research Journal*, 6(3), 276-292. <http://dergipark.ulakbim.gov.tr/eltrj/>.
- Llurda, E. (2005). Non-Native TESOL Students as seen by Practicum Supervisors. *Non-Native Language Teachers*, 131-154. doi:10.1007/0-387-24565-0_8.
- Payant, C. & Murphy, J. (2012). Cooperating teachers' roles and responsibilities in a MATESOL practicum. *TESL Canada Journal*, 29(2), 1-23.
- Popping, R. (2015). Analyzing open-ended questions by means of text analysis procedures. *Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 128, 23-39. Doi: 10.1177/0759106315597389.
- Subedi, D. (2016). explanatory sequential mixed method design as the third research community of knowledge claim. *American Journal of Educational Research*, (4), 7, 570-577.
- Sepulveda-Escobar, P. & Morrison, A. (2020). Online teaching placement during the COVID-19 pandemic in Chile: challenges and opportunities. *European Journal Of Teacher Education*, 43 (4), 587-607 <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1820981>.
- TEDMEM. (2020). COVID-19 sürecinde eğitim: Uzaktan öğrenme, sorunlar ve çözüm önerileri (TEDMEM Analiz Dizisi 7). Ankara: Türk Eğitim Derneği Yayınları.7). Ankara: Türk Eğitim Derneği Yayınları. <https://tedmem.org/yayin/covid-19-surecinde-egitim-uzaktan-ogrenme-sorunlar-cozum-onerileri>.
- Tüfekçi-Can, D. & Baştürk, M. (2018). QUSLITATIVE research: the pre-service EFL teachers' opinions on teaching practicum. *H. U. Journal of Education*, 28(3), 97-110. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/495666>.
- Tüm, D.Ö& Kunt, N. (2013). Speaking anxiety among EFL student teachers. *H. U. Journal of Education*, 28(3), 385-399.
- Yalçın Arslan, F & İlin, G .(2018). The effects of teaching practicum on EFL pre-service teachers' concerns . *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 14(2), 265-282. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/jlls/issue/43364/527979>.
- Yan, C & He, C. (2010) Transforming the existing model of teaching practicum: a study of Chinese EFL student teachers' perceptions, *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 36:1, 57-73, DOI: 10.1080/02607470903462065.
- Yazan, B. (2016). Early career EFL teachers' instructional challenges. *Journal of Theory and Practice in Education*, 12(1), 194-220.
- Yuan, L.& Lee, I. (2014). Pre-service teachers' changing beliefs in the teaching practicum: Three cases in an EFL context. *System*, 44, 1-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2014.02.002>.
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